

ISic3200

I.Sicily inscription 3200

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

greeting

Material

mosaic (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR114090

1. χαῖρε σύ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285008

EDR 114090

EDCS 64900513

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 01.0417

Gabricsi, E. 1921. Ruderii romani scoperti alla Piazza della Vittoria in Palermo. *Monumenti Antichi*. 27: 181-204. At 197 dr

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